

CHAKHAO KHEER

Manipuri Black Aromatic Rice Pudding

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Photos by Thoithoi Khaidem

Chakhao Kheer is the sweet dish (dessert) made of black aromatic rice (also known as forbidden rice), milk and sugar as main ingredient. It is almost similar with the *kheer* known in India subcontinent. It is also flavored with cardamom, raisins or dry nuts. Literally *chakhao* means delicious rice. In Manipur black aromatic rice is believed to have been brought by Poireiton and his horde, one of the progenitors of Meiteis,

when they first came to settle in the valley. So, black aromatic rice is also known as *Poireiton Chakhao*.

The recipe is made the same way as white rice *Kheer*. It is served in the major feast of Manipur as a dessert. No temple feast is considered complete without *Kheer* dessert. The aroma and flavor of the Chakhao kheer is one of the uniqueness of the dish. It is also known for its health

INGREDIENTS

1 Cup black aromatic rice

1 litre milk

½ cup sugar

Few cardamom pods

Raisin

Dry nuts

Shredded coconut for garnish

Step 1

Step 2

Step 3

METHOD

- 1) Rinse the black aromatic rice and soak it in water for a minimum of 30 min (preferably soak for overnight)
- 2) Cook the black aromatic rice (like we cook normal rice) in a pressure cooker or rice cooker. Cooked black aromatic rice is served with white rice kheer in traditional feast of the Meitei and taken by combining both.
- 3) Heat the milk in a pot and put the cooked black aromatic rice.
- 4) Add sugar, cardamom and raisin. Stir it continuously.
- 5) Allow it to simmer until you get the desire consistency.
- 6) Turn off the flame and garnish it with dry nuts and shredded coconut.
- 7) Chakhao Kheer is ready to serve hot or chill it in a fridge to serve later as cold dessert.

Step 4